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Towards improved representation of distributional impacts of climate change and mitigation policies in model scenarios

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E-mail: s.g.kulkarni@uu.nl**Keywords:** climate change, mitigation, burden-sharing, carbon tax, climate damages, gini index, suits index**Abstract**

Climate mitigation policies and climate change damages can have unequal incidences both between and within countries. This paper examines the under-explored dynamics of within-country distributional impacts, focusing on residential energy expenditures and avoided climate change damages resulting from climate policies, using the Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment (IMAGE). By looking at energy expenditures for different income groups for residential energy consumption, we find that - without redistributive policies - climate mitigation action achieved via carbon prices alone could disproportionately affect poorer population groups. This is the result of both changes in relative energy costs and high up-front investment needs for low-carbon solutions. At the same time, poorer population groups would likely benefit the most from the same mitigation action through avoided damages. Overall, this might lead to a net-progressive outcome. The presented scenario analysis indicates the need for equitable policies to protect low-income groups, particularly in low-income regions vulnerable to the largest impacts of climate change.

1. Introduction

In its Sixth Assessment Report, the IPCC WGII has concluded that not all people are equally exposed to climate risks (IPCC 2022b). More recent research confirmed this finding, both in terms of climate impacts and mitigation (Hsiang *et al* 2019, Malpede and Percoco 2021, Bistline *et al* 2024, Cortés Arbués *et al* 2024, Méjean *et al* 2024, Spinoni *et al* 2024). Climate impacts are found to disproportionately affect the poor, given higher levels of exposure and a lower ability to adapt. Climate mitigation could exacerbate existing inequalities as well, as it could lead to increasing energy costs for lower income groups.

Without additional measures to alleviate such potential regressive impacts, other societal goals, such as poverty alleviation, will become more difficult to achieve. Furthermore, injustice (real or perceived) can seriously undermine support for climate policy (Lamb *et al* 2020, Feindt *et al* 2021, Ewald *et al* 2022). Reduced public support can influence the stringency or ambition level of national climate policies (Konc *et al* 2022), risking increased climate impacts or the need for even more stringent mitigation action in the long run (Guivarch and Rogelj 2017). Societal acceptance of climate policies is thus critical and this depends on improved understanding of who bears the costs of mitigation and benefits of avoided damages, and how mitigation policies can be designed to ensure fairer outcomes (van den Berg *et al* 2020, Wang *et al* 2016, World Bank 2024).

Existing literature on within-country distributional impacts of climate change policy mostly focus on case studies scoped to a single country or group of countries using relatively low carbon taxes (World Bank 2024) or with short time scales (see (Wang *et al* 2016) for a comprehensive overview). Integrated assessment models (IAMs) studies have mainly focused on fair distributions of mitigation action between countries (Du Pont *et al* 2016, Okereke and Coventry 2016, Robiou Du Pont *et al* 2017, Holz *et al* 2018, Leimbach and

Giannousakis 2019, van den Berg *et al* 2020, Pan *et al* 2023), sometimes also accounting that climate change impacts are distributed unequally (Hof *et al* 2010, de Cian *et al* 2016, Taconet *et al* 2020). An exception is a recent article in which the Global Change Analysis Model (GCAM) IAM is used to analyse the residential energy demand and expenditures across income deciles of different socio-economic and climate futures (Sampedro *et al* 2024), but this article does not explicitly report on the regressivity or progressivity of mitigation policy and avoided climate impacts.

The present paper fills this gap by analysing the impact of mitigation on residential energy expenditures of different income groups in large world regions, and compares these with estimated (avoided) damages, using the Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment (IMAGE). The key aim is to improve our understanding of these impacts to better inform just climate policies. Towards this end, distributional impacts are indexed along two dimensions: regressivity i.e., how the policy impacts are distributed across income groups, and inequality i.e., how the unequal distribution across income groups affect disposable incomes inequality. All further references to regressivity and impacts to income inequality in this article use this terminology for consistency (further elaborated in section 2.3).

2. Methods

2.1. Overall framework

We apply a scenario analysis method using the IMAGE 3.4 integrated assessment modelling framework (Stehfest *et al* 2014) that simulates interactions between human activities and the environment. The framework consists of a detailed representation of energy, land-use and climate systems through several sub-models and has been widely used to explore alternative climate change mitigation scenarios and implications of climate policy. The model has full global coverage divided into 26 world regions and typically runs scenarios to project outcomes until 2100.

The TIMER energy systems sub-model—particularly the residential energy module (Daioglou *et al* 2012), and the MIMOSA cost-benefit assessment module (van der Wijst *et al* 2021)—are the most relevant sub-models of the IMAGE framework for this study (figure 1). While the former covers the energy demand and costs for different income groups, the latter describes the climate impacts. Below, we describe the aspects of the model that are most relevant to this study, while further detail is provided in the [appendix](#) (section A1). A detailed account of the IMAGE modelling framework is available on the IMAGE wiki website (Netherlands Environmental Agency (PBL), [n.d.](#)).

The calculations for each scenario are as follows. We derive residential energy costs across income quintiles using the TIMER model. In parallel, we use MIMOSA to derive first-order estimates of aggregate regional damages which we distribute across income quintiles. These two parallel runs are done for baseline and climate change mitigation scenarios (See section 2.5). The scenario outcomes of TIMER and MIMOSA are compared to explore the impacts on energy expenditures and climate damages respectively, and as well as their combined impacts using distributional indices (see section 2.4).

2.2. Modelling residential energy demand

The residential energy model of IMAGE simulates energy supply and demand. Demand is determined for five income quintiles for urban as well as rural households for 26 world regions across six energy functions: cooking, space heating, space cooling, water heating, and appliances (Daioglou *et al* 2012, van Ruijven *et al* 2011).

The energy demand for each end-use function is driven by exogenous projections of socio-economic characteristics, including total household expenditures and population growth, and endogenously determined intermediate drivers such as electrification rates, household size, floor space, and climate conditions (see figure A1 in the appendix). Total household expenditures are used as a proxy for incomes, a common practice in economics literature given the inconsistent nature of income data (see for example Tables 2.1–3.11 in (Kojima *et al* 2010)). We estimate the distribution of total household expenditures with a log-normal functional form, with the shape parameter defined using the Gini index and the scale parameter by the total household expenditures share of GDP per capita (see section A1 in the appendix). On the supply side, eight fuels (energy carriers) are represented in the model: solid fuels, liquid fuels, gaseous fuels, traditional biofuels, modern biofuels, hydrogen, secondary heat, and electricity.

The model allocates fuel shares to meet energy demand for each end-use function, using a multinomial logit function accounting for the availability and relative costs of the fuels, but also taking into account capital costs for the relevant end-use technologies. Furthermore, households can also adopt efficiency measures, such as insulation, to reduce their energy demand—dictated by the relative costs of insulation versus heating (see appendix, section A1.1). As households get richer, consumer discount rates (i.e., how they perceive the costs of advanced technologies over their lifetime) reduce—and thus their incentive to buy expensive technologies increases. This affects investments in energy efficiency or cleaner fuels, which may have significant upfront costs for certain demographics. The model thus represents the concept of energy and efficiency ladders, i.e., households tend to switch to cleaner, more efficient, and more convenient fuels with higher upfront investments with increasing income (van Ruijven *et al* 2015). The energy demand module has been calibrated for the 1971–2022 period in order to reproduce historical trends in fuel and electricity use as presented by the IEA energy balances. Historic data on population, private consumption, energy prices, household sizes, residential building types, floorspace, appliance ownership, and fuel use are used wherever available to aid with the calibration.

The costs of primary energy carriers in TIMER are based on supply curves of energy carriers, which may change over time due to technological learning or depletion. In mitigation scenarios, the application of carbon pricing and associated increase in energy prices has two effects in the residential sector: a shift towards the adoption of non-fossil energy carriers, including electricity and modern bio-energy, and a reduction in total energy demand due to adoption of efficiency measures. The model determines the expenditures paid for residential energy services through incident fuel prices and demand levels for each end-use.

In the mitigation scenarios, the socio-economic characteristics and activity levels driving total energy demand remain the same as in the baseline scenario. However, the presence of a carbon price affects fuel choices through the multinomial logit function. Moreover, the same demand for energy service (e.g. space or water heating, appliance use) is met by a smaller (larger) final energy demand as the representative agents make choices towards more (less) energy efficient options available to them. Furthermore, as climate policy affects the price of electricity, the expenditures for electricity-based energy services (appliances, lighting, space cooling) are also affected.

TIMER is not an economic equilibrium model, but a recursive dynamic simulation model with a focus on the energy system and associated energy flows. Thus, the model ensures that physical flows (energy resources, carbon, etc) balance out, but not necessarily monetary flows. This means that the determined residential energy expenditures are not constrained in the model by other expenditures towards taxes, food, housing, savings, or consumption of other goods and services. Non-energy expenditures are also not affected by introducing a carbon price. Although capital expenditures at the household level (such as for insulation, increased floor space, appliance ownership), as well as capital costs of associated public infrastructure (e.g., piped gas networks) influence the modelled household energy choices, the present analysis focuses on energy expenditures associated with fuel prices. Since demanded energy services in mitigation scenarios are maintained at the same level as in the baseline, additional energy expenditures and climate impacts may amount to very high shares of total household expenditures, especially for the lowest income groups. Such results are an indication that households cannot afford the same energy service demand levels anymore, highlighting the need to implement additional policies to protect them.

2.3. Estimating distribution of (avoided) climate impacts

Unlike energy expenditures that are first modelled bottom up and then aggregated to the regional levels, damage estimates are calculated first at the regional level before disaggregation across income groups for each

scenario. Mean per-capita damage costs for the 26 world regions are calculated using the MIMOSA model (van der Wijst *et al* 2021). Climate impacts, and especially their economic valuation, are very uncertain (Howard and Sterner 2017, Hsiang *et al* 2019, Cortés Arbués *et al* 2024). Cost-benefit integrated assessment models such as MIMOSA typically use reduced-form damage functions that relate global temperature change to economic losses. We use the COACCH damage function (Bosello *et al* 2012) which estimates economic losses corresponding to physical climate impacts using a computable general equilibrium approach. This damage function represents a step forward in this area of study by covering a broad range of sectors in climate impact models, viz agriculture, forestry, fishery, energy demand, energy supply, labour supply, riverine floods, transportation, and sea-level rise (van der Wijst *et al* 2023). Furthermore, the approach allows an internally consistent treatment of sectoral uncertainties into the overall damage estimation that can be parametrised in integrated scenario analyses. In the present analysis we mainly use estimates with the median (50th percentile) specification. Further detail on the coverage of climate impacts quantified by the COACCH function, and how they compare with other commonly used damage functions are given in the appendix (section A1.3).

The distribution of the aggregate damages across income quintiles is done by using an income elasticity to damages, as estimated in a recent study which uses a novel method involving the downscaling of global and country-level damage functions to quantify distributional impacts within countries (Gilli *et al* 2023). The study empirically supports the hypothesis that lower income groups have a lesser adaptive capacity to insulate themselves from the economic impacts of increased temperatures, and thus disproportionately bear the consequences of unmitigated climate impacts. The income elasticity of climate impacts is then calculated per country, relating the relative incidence of damages to changes in income levels within countries as follows:

$$\left(\frac{\text{Damage costs}_{rt}^q}{\text{Damage costs}_{rt}} \right) = a_{rt} \left(\frac{\text{Income}_{rt}^q}{\text{Income}_{rt}} \right)^{\xi_r} \quad (1)$$

where damage shares of the q th quintile in region r relate to their respective income shares by elasticity ξ and scaling factor a . The study reports a global average income elasticity robust to the choice of damage functions at 0.7. Elasticity values below 1 indicate the overall regressivity of climate change impacts.

For each scenario, we implement the population weighted country level elasticities to estimate damages incident across income quintiles following equation (1). The distribution of damages is modelled across regional income quintiles without an urban-rural disaggregation, since we do not have information on the distribution of damages to urban and rural areas. In a similar vein to the treatment of quintile-level energy expenditures (section 2.2 above), we do not endogenously adjust income levels for damage costs.

2.4. Estimating distributional impacts of carbon pricing

For each scenario, we implement the population weighted country level elasticities to estimate damages incident across income quintiles following equation (1). The distribution of damages is modelled across regional income quintiles without an urban-rural disaggregation, since we do not have information on the distribution of damages to urban and rural areas. We calculate the change in energy expenditures between a mitigation and baseline scenario for all income groups. The (change in) energy burden is defined as the (change in the) ratio of energy expenditures to total household expenditures (equation (2)). Equivalently, we calculate the difference between the incident damages in a mitigation and baseline scenario (avoided damages) for each quintile and determine the respective changes in damage burdens (equation (3)). Two summary statistic measures, the Suits index and Gini coefficient, are then derived to analyse the distributional consequences of these unequal impacts.

$$\Delta \text{Energy Burden}_{1.50C}^q = \left(\frac{\text{Energy Expenditure}_{1.50C}^q - \text{Energy Expenditure}_{BL}^q}{\text{Total household expenditures}_{BL}^q} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta \text{Damage Burden}_{1.50C}^q = \left(\frac{\text{Damage costs}_{1.50C}^q - \text{Damage costs}_{BL}^q}{\text{Total household expenditures}_{BL}^q} \right) \quad (3)$$

The Gini index and Suits index are statistical summary indicators, both summarizing inequality but capturing different aspects.

The Gini index is derived from Lorenz curves and measures the degree of inequality in the distribution of income (or expenditure) across a population. It quantifies the deviation of income distribution from a perfectly equal distribution, with values ranging from 0 (perfect equality) to 1 (maximum inequality), or equivalently over the range (0, 100). The consequences of modelled carbon pricing and climate damages on disposable income inequality are captured by comparing the Gini coefficients after energy expenditures and incident damage costs between the mitigation and baseline scenarios. A positive (negative) change indicates increasing (decreasing) income inequalities attributed to the respective mitigation scenario.

The Suits Index uses the concept of Relative Concentration Curves (such as Lorenz curves used for the Gini index) to determine the ratio of the cumulative share of tax incident on the p th percentile of the population to its cumulative share of income. Values are bound by the interval $(-1, 1)$ or equivalently by $(-100, 100)$, with -100 implying that the tax is entirely incident on the lowest group (most regressive) and $+100$ implying that the tax is entirely incident on the highest (most progressive). We calculate the progressivity or regressivity of mitigation scenarios through changing energy expenditure and damage burdens, and their combined impact. An overview of the index and its formulation is given in the appendix (section A3).

The Gini index measures overall income inequality across the population, while the Suits index (Suits 1977, Jiang and Shao 2014, Feindt *et al* 2021, Fragkos *et al* 2021, Köppl and Schratzenstaller 2023) focuses specifically on whether the increases of the energy expenditures is distributed progressively (falling more on the rich) or regressively (falling more on the poor). This distinction between the distributional aspects captured by the two indices helps explain why small increases in income inequality, as reflected in small increases in the Gini index, can be seen alongside different movements in the Suits index.

For example, if increased carbon prices cause a relatively small additional cost for the poorest households, it may be small enough that it does not substantially affect overall income inequality. In this case the Gini index may show little change. However, if this small cost is a larger share of the poor households' incomes compared to the richer ones, the Suits index would show a regressive outcome (decreasing Suits values). Conversely, if higher-income households face higher absolute energy cost increases, roughly proportional to their income levels, and poorer households face smaller relative increases, the Gini index may still show little overall change, but the Suits index could indicate a slight shift toward progressive distributional outcomes (increasing Suits values). Thus, differences in the movements of the two indices reflect whether the energy cost burden is relatively heavier on the poor or rich, even if the overall change in income inequality remains small.

2.5. Scenarios

In the analysis, we focus on a baseline and two mitigation scenarios. All three scenarios are driven by the same socioeconomic variables (e.g., GDP growth, population growth, Gini coefficients, and urbanisation levels) of the 'middle-of-the road' SSP2 Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (Riahi *et al* 2017). The baseline scenario is defined by no additional mitigation action, whereas in the mitigation scenarios the end-of-century global average temperature increase is limited to 1.5 °C with a greater than 50% probability, and 2 °C with a 67% probability.

The additional energy expenditures in the 1.5 °C and 2 °C mitigation scenarios result from a globally uniform carbon price from 2025 onwards. We focus on a global uniform carbon price not because we assume that this is the most realistic or just form of climate policy (in fact, earlier studies have found that a universal carbon price in fact leads to unfair outcomes between countries (Du Pont *et al* 2016, Okereke and Coventry 2016, Taconet *et al* 2020, Pan *et al* 2023)), but because this allows better interpretation of the underlying dynamics and results. Recent efforts aim to incorporate more plausible regional differentiation in mitigation scenarios (Bertram *et al* 2024); however, there is currently no consensus in academic literature or among policymakers on the topic.

The carbon prices are determined endogenously in the IMAGE model framework to meet specific climate targets (carbon price and corresponding global emission profiles shown in figure 2) based on the lowest global costs. A more detailed explanation of how they are derived and the assumptions that underpin their trajectories can be found in (van Vuuren *et al* 2007).

All monetary data is converted into constant 2005 USD prices in IMAGE model. Unless otherwise specified, all further monetary values presented in this article are also expressed in 2005 USD terms.

3. Results

3.1. Distribution of additional energy expenditures

In both mitigation scenarios, implementation of carbon prices leads to increased energy expenditures relative to baseline. Globally, the strongest increase in expenditures is observed in the short term after the carbon prices are implemented. Differences in absolute energy expenditures between regions already present in the baseline are exacerbated in the mitigation scenarios (figure A5). For most regions, mean per-capita energy expenditures initially increase upon the introduction of carbon prices and decrease after this initial peak. The extent to which energy expenditures increase in mitigation scenarios, as well as how close to baseline levels they return to by the end of the century, varies across regions. These variations are due to differences in current energy mixes and how different income groups in different regions respond to carbon pricing, as explained in more detail below.

Figure 3 shows the change in energy burden (i.e., additional energy costs as share of total household expenditures) for the poorest and richest quintiles in the 1.5 °C scenario in selected world regions, grouped by time periods. The increase in energy burden for the poorest quintile is an order of magnitude higher than for the richest quintile. As the demanded energy services as well as the total household expenditures for each quintile

are unchanged between the baseline and mitigation scenarios, the differences are solely attributed to changes in fuel prices.

There are three main reasons why the change in energy burden is larger for poorer households. The first reason is simply that the same absolute increase in fossil fuel prices leads to greater changes in energy burdens among lower income quintiles, as their overall expenditures are lower. Secondly, high income quintiles are better positioned to make choices towards decarbonising their energy demand. They already exhibit high electrification rates (and electricity access) across residential end-uses and tend to use lower-emitting fuels in the baseline (figure 4). Richer households are also more likely to invest in efficiency measures and cleaner energy

technologies (including heat pumps, rooftop PV, insulation, etc (Gernaat *et al* 2020, Daioglou *et al* 2022)) due to lower discount rates. These features can help explain why many high-income households may incur only marginal additional costs in the mitigation scenario compared to their already favourable baseline. Coupled with expected energy efficiency gains over the century, this also explains why higher income quintiles are likelier to incur lower energy expenditure relative to baseline projections in the long term.

Conversely, poorer quintiles that do not have the means to invest in cleaner options or do not have access to electricity and so-called modern energy sources stick longer to fossil-based fuels (with disproportionate carbon price effects making them more expensive). They are also likelier to revert to traditional biomass which is not subject to carbon pricing (figure 4). This represents shifts down the so-called energy ladder, despite increasing income levels over time for all quintiles. These results highlight that poorer households may face important barriers to moving towards cleaner fuels, while also suffering disproportionately from the carbon prices, while their overall emissions are typically lower compared to richer households' (figures A12–A15).

While these described model dynamics explain a majority of the presented results, regional differences in the share of renewables in electricity generation also play a role in the availability and affordability of the choices available to all households within as reflected in figure 4 for rural quintiles (also see figure A11 for urban quintiles). For example, initial high impacts in Russia, Western Africa and South Africa regions (figure 3) also correspond with low renewable shares in electricity generation before the carbon prices are introduced. Even as households transition to electricity to meet their demanded residential energy services, they are exposed to more expensive electricity prices until the electricity production gets decarbonised under the same carbon price signal (figure A20).

Not all regions and modelled income groups show an increase in energy burdens relative to baseline. In Brazil, for instance, changes in energy burden are negative, with the poorest income quintile benefitting more than the richest (figure 3). This is explained in part by the low dependence of the poorest quintiles on fossil fuels for residential energy needs in the baseline, since they predominantly use either traditional biofuels or electricity. In mitigation scenarios, they respond to high carbon prices by increased use of traditional biofuels, and are thus relatively less affected in expenditure terms compared to rich quintiles who reduce (but not completely eliminate) their fossil-based energy demand. Aided by already high shares of renewables in their electricity mix, the net result is the observed negative values for their energy burden change relative to baseline.

The global average annual additional energy costs for households resulting from the carbon price amounts to about USD (2005) 450 per capita between 2025 and 2100 in the 1.5 °C scenario and USD (2005) 78 in the 2 °C scenario.

3.2. Distribution of avoided damages

Damage estimates in all three scenarios increase over time in all regions, but there are strong regional differences in damage levels. In the baseline SSP2, mean per-capita damages are projected to be the highest in Sub-Saharan African regions, India, Southeast Asian regions, and the lowest in Europe, Central Asia, the Middle East and Russia. Meeting the emission targets represented by the mitigation scenarios greatly reduce damages in all regions at the aggregate level, as well as for all population groups within. Differences in the distributional impacts from avoided damages (equation (3)) are nearly indiscernible between the two mitigation scenarios modelled. Estimated damages in the baseline scenario are up to an order of magnitude higher, compared to both the 1.5 °C and the 2 °C mitigation scenarios (figure A21), reflecting the universal benefits from climate mitigation in the long term.

Implementation of income elasticities of damages from (Gilli *et al* 2023) lead to unequal distribution of damage costs for population groups within regions, with poorer households experiencing higher damages in a given scenario than richer ones. Subsequently, when analysing the impact differences between baseline and mitigation scenarios, poorer households stand to benefit more than richer ones from avoided damages (figure 5 and A21). On average across world regions, the bottom income quintile benefits twice as much from avoided damages in a 1.5 °C mitigation scenario than the top quintile in the same region. In poorer and warmer world regions, which are already known to be more vulnerable to climate change impacts, the relative benefit of the poorest quintiles is up to 6 times as large as the richest quintiles in the stringent mitigation scenario.

3.3. Impacts on distributional indicators

3.3.1. Energy expenditures

The unequal distribution of additional energy expenditures and avoided damages are reflected in the regressivity indicators. Figure 6 shows the regional variation in the Suits index in the two mitigation scenarios for selected regions. The negative values indicate that carbon prices have a regressive impact across income groups (i.e., the policies disproportionately impact poorer incomes). The Suits index reveals large differences in the regressivity of the carbon price between regions. The regressivity is the highest in Russia, Western Africa,

Figure 5. Avoided per capita climate damages per capita (as fraction of total household expenditures per capita in 1.5 °C mitigation scenario relative to baseline for poorest and richest quintiles in selected model regions, (a) Short term, (b) Mid term, (c) Long term.

and South Africa, especially in the medium and long term, reflecting the high additional energy burden for the poorest quintiles in these regions. This is due to the differences in fossil fuel phase out among the constituent quintiles seen in section 3.1 above, and the share of total expenditures represented by any remaining fossil fuel use among the poorer quintiles. In all other selected regions, there is no regressivity in the long term.

While there are some differences in the degree of regressivity between urban and rural areas, the variation across regions and mitigation scenarios is too large for a consistent picture. Outcomes are also not significantly more regressive in the 1.5 °C scenario than in the 2 °C scenario, only the magnitude of changes are higher due to the higher carbon prices.

Both mitigation scenarios result in more unequal outcomes relative to baseline as measured by Gini impacts (figure 7). Inequality increases sharply in almost all world regions shortly after the introduction of a carbon price, reducing significantly after the initial peak to baseline levels by the end of the century. Increase in inequalities are greater in the 1.5 °C scenario (regional average peak +2.4 points) than in the 2 °C scenario (regional average peak +0.7 points). Some middle-income regions in Asia and the Americas are even projected to be less unequal in the long term in the 1.5 °C scenario compared to the baseline, albeit to a very small degree (< -0.2 points Gini change). Impacts in rural areas are slightly higher than in urban areas.

The difference in the initial peak in increased inequality reflects current differences in fossil-fuel dependency between regions. In this initial period, all households in regions with high fossil-fuel dependency face high energy burdens, with poorer households being affected more than richer ones. Later in the century as carbon price ramp up, the availability and affordability of alternative carbon-free fuels strongly determine inequality outcomes. Regions like Russia where decarbonised electricity remains expensive into the long term

Figure 6. Suits index for unequal energy expenditure impacts in mitigation scenarios relative to Baseline (selected world regions).

(due to low renewable shares in electricity production in the absence of carbon pricing) show the longest enduring inequality impacts. Other regions where households face obstacles in moving up the ladder from high initial shares of natural gas to electricity also show strong inequality impacts into the longer term. High increases in income inequalities are for instance seen in Sub-Saharan African regions, where poorer households remain partially dependent on fossil fuels for some energy services (e.g., kerosene for lighting and cooking). On the other hand, developed regions such as Western Europe, Canada, USA, Japan, Korea, and Oceania show low increases in inequality, since the increased energy costs represent lower shares of household's expenditures.

The universally observed dynamics of decreasing Gini changes after the peak in all regions and in both scenarios reflect the degree to which all income groups transition to energy sources that are not carbon priced. However, an important caveat to this behaviour is the increased—or at least not reduced—dependence of many poorer quintiles on traditional biofuels such as firewood or dung cakes (also see figure 4). This marks an energy transition opposite to the desired direction of increased uptake of cleaner energy sources.

3.3.1.1. Damages

Both the statistical summary indicators reflect the income elasticities of damages used to calculate them, and highlight the distributional benefits of achieving mitigation targets.

Predominantly positive values of the Suits index in figure 8 (top panel) indicate the progressive nature of avoided damages when respective emission targets are met in the mitigation scenarios. The benefits of avoided damages are more progressive for low- and middle-income regions in Central and South Americas, Asia and Africa that are characterised by low-income elasticity values determined in work by Gilli and colleagues (Gilli *et al* 2023). The Suits indices for the distribution of damages only vary slightly over time for all regions, with the variation attributable to increasing total damages.

Unequal benefits of avoided climate damages in both mitigation scenarios are reflected by corresponding changes to the Gini coefficient (defined here with total household expenditures reduced by incident damage costs, see methods). Both mitigation scenarios lead to decreased Gini values on average across regions from about 0.09 points in the short term to 1.73 in the long term. However, the regions with low income elasticities to damages and high aggregate regional damages see a much more pronounced impact over time with Gini

coefficients decreasing by up to 10 points in the long term (figure 8, bottom panel). One must be careful in interpreting the decrease in the Gini coefficient not as an active reduction of income inequalities, but rather as their avoided Increase in the absence of a mitigation policy.

3.3.1.2. Combined impacts—energy expenditures and damages

Following the temporal trends of the Suits index calculated for energy expenditures and damages, their combined impacts indicate mostly neutral distributional impacts among regions (near-zero Suits index values), with modestly progressive impacts in the long term (predominantly positive Suits index values) in both mitigation scenarios (figure 9).

Similarly, the combined impact to income inequalities (Gini change) follows from the opposing time trends seen for additional energy expenditures and avoided damages. Higher energy expenditures in mitigation scenarios dominate the combined impacts in the short term, resulting in small net increase in income inequalities (near-zero Gini change relative to baseline). However, in the mid to long term, achieving mitigation targets avoids a greater degree of increased income inequalities from avoided damages in vulnerable regions.

4. Discussion

In this study, we present the distributional impact of introducing carbon pricing to limit global temperature change to 1.5 °C and well below 2 °C at a sub-national level. Using the IMAGE model framework, we capture the impacts through two key channels represented in the model: changing residential energy expenditures and avoided climate damage costs. We distinguish between regressivity of impacts (proportionality of impacts

borne across increasing incomes) using the Suits index, and the impact on income inequality using the Gini index. While the terms regressivity and income inequality are sometimes used interchangeably in literature to refer to the Gini impact alone, the distinction can help policymakers develop fairer, socially acceptable climate policies. This is a first effort of capturing within-country/region distributional effects of climate policy on both energy expenditures and climate change damages, with some caveats that are important to take into account.

The residential sector representation in the IMAGE model focuses particularly on the expenditures on energy sources to capture the modelled distribution of mitigation impacts. These expenditures are directly influenced by mitigation policies modelled through carbon prices, and we show how they result in regressive distributional outcomes. However, capital investments and operational costs of devices and infrastructure at the household level are not included, nor public infrastructure expenditures to ensure access to appropriate energy sources as households move up the energy ladder. While some of these additional capital expenditures are not explicitly captured, they should be taken into account while designing a just redistribution policy. Increasing carbon prices may also have distributional consequences through other channels than those considered in this model. For example, in addition to residential energy expenditures, they also affect households unequally via changes in expenditures on personal transport or food. Currently, the transport and food sectors are modelled at the regional level of aggregation in IMAGE (Netherlands Environmental Agency (PBL) 2025). Future model development can integrate a broader set of distributional channels of mitigation policy impacts and inform a more holistic multisectoral redistributive policies using combined revenues.

Although our model results show that the impact of carbon prices on residential energy expenditure is likely to be regressive in most regions in the short term, a comprehensive review of the case-study literature by Wang and colleagues (Wang *et al* 2016), and a recent meta-analysis by Ohlendorf and colleagues (Ohlendorf *et al* 2021) indicate a likelihood of some progressive outcomes in developing regions. This is typically explained by lower ownership levels of energy-consuming devices (appliances, private vehicles etc) by poorer households than richer ones in these regions. Poorer households are thus expected to spend a lower share of their total expenditures on energy. Any increase in fuel prices would therefore disproportionately affect richer households. However, limited empirical evidence from developing countries in Asia and Africa indicate that expenditure shares on residential energy services addressed in the present study decrease along increasing income quintiles (in contrast to household expenditures on transport-related energy costs—which do indeed increase with income) (Kojima *et al* 2010). Additionally, the reviewed studies in literature indicating progressive outcomes in developing regions differ from our approach in two significant ways. First, they involve carbon taxes much lower than needed to meet Paris Agreement targets. Second, they do not model households' dynamic responses of switching to a more affordable fuel type. Still, Ohlendorf *et al* find that studies that account for dynamic demand-side responses to increased fossil-fuel prices and cross-sectoral interaction effects typical of general equilibrium and microsimulation models are more likely to show progressive distributional impacts from introducing carbon taxes. However, the apparently progressive outcomes come at the cost of lowered demand for energy services, which might have particularly dire consequences concerning energy access for the poorest households.

While it is clear that mitigation scenarios lead to economically beneficial outcomes in the long term, assessing their distributional consequences is challenging. Estimates of climate damages, i.e., economic losses from increasing climate impacts, as well as their incidence across income groups within regions, are uncertain. We implement the most recent approach to modelling within-country distribution of incident damages that may be applied top-down to global scale models combined with a median estimation of aggregate damages. The COACCH damage function used here does not yet include economic evaluations of climate change impacts through biodiversity loss, or through changes in health and mortality indices (although through impacts to labour productivity are included)—which would increase the aggregate damage estimates (Bosello *et al* 2012, Rising *et al* 2022). In a similar vein to climate policy impacts, physical climate change impacts and their economic damage estimates may have distributional impact through other channels than those estimated using the chosen damage function. With higher damage estimates, poorer households in poorer countries would consequently likely stand to gain more from successfully achieved mitigation targets than our findings show, with the progressive distribution of benefits contrasting even more with the regressivity of carbon-pricing in the residential energy sector sans equitable redistributions.

Climate damages and increased carbon prices can also have unequal impacts on the baseline income distribution itself, such as through changes in sectoral employment, reduced aggregate consumption, inter-sectoral and inter-channel interactions, or through hitherto unmodelled impacts on population size and migration, health and mortality, and peace and conflict (McLeman and Smit 2006, Hallegatte *et al* 2016). These interactions and feedbacks are better captured by other modelling paradigms such as microsimulation and general equilibrium models (Skoufias *et al* 2011, van Ruijven *et al* 2015, Kuiper and Zeist 2023), or health and demographic models. However, these models add much greater uncertainty, especially over long time scales. Our approach ensures that the unequal distribution of the costs and benefits of climate mitigation as well as the need to protect the most vulnerable recipients are identified along long-term scenario pathways.

Distributional effects are highly sensitive to assumptions on the logarithmic functional form of income distribution (van Ruijven *et al* 2015). Due to data limitations, we estimate impacts at the mean income level per quintile, obscuring horizontal intra-quintile variations of incident impacts. While the relationship between climate impact incidence and income is significant enough for the scope of this study, capturing heterogeneity

of climate impacts across other dimensions such as spatial location, age, gender, and employment sectors, could help develop policies aiding the most vulnerable further within each income quintile.

The mitigation scenarios are represented by globally uniform carbon prices based on lowest global costs, without fairness considerations such as the capacity to reduce emissions or responsibility in order to be consistent with most scenarios in the literature (IPCC 2022a, World Bank 2024). This approach is criticized because efficiency is valued more than equity. Moreover, the feasibility of implementing such a policy instrument has been questioned, and alternatives have been proposed (D'Autume *et al* 2016, Abrell *et al* 2018, Verbruggen and Brauers 2020). Others propose alternative regional differentiation in carbon prices with a focus on effectiveness in achieved emission reduction (Boeters 2014), equitable outcomes (Boroumand *et al* 2022, Chateau *et al* 2024), or even sectoral differentiation within regions (Landis *et al* 2018). An existing branch of literature actively delves into articulating fair burden-sharing alternatives through regionally differentiated carbon prices (Dennig *et al* 2015, Leimbach and Giannousakis 2019). However, there is scant political or academic consensus on what may be considered as a realistic or feasible allocation of differentiated carbon prices. With our approach of using global uniform carbon prices, results can be interpreted more easily. However, future work evaluating the within-region distributional consequences of burden-sharing regimes could further aid in developing just transition policies.

As carbon pricing as a standalone policy instrument can lead to disproportionate burden on poor and exacerbated income inequalities, redistributive policies are imperative in ensuring broad societal support. Most literature addressing distributional concerns assume a recycling of the generated revenues as a lump-sum transfers (Kallbekken *et al* 2011, Emmerling and Tavoni 2021, Steckel *et al* 2021, Orbons *et al* 2024). These transfers often do not go beyond redistributing revenues on an equal per capita basis, irrespective of differences in socio-economic status or climate vulnerability. Studies focused on specific countries in specific years do include a broader set of compensatory policy mechanisms. Broadly, these may be classified as targeted compensation, investments in improving education and awareness, investments in green energy infrastructure and energy transition, and contribution to global climate funding efforts (Carattini *et al* 2018, Andersson and Atkinson 2020, Douenne and Fabre 2020, Gaikwad *et al* 2022).

In addition to direct transfers of recycled revenues, targeted compensation covers a broad spectrum of mechanisms, such as carbon tax rebates on the poorest, subsidising and promoting uptake of energy-efficient clean technology devices (e.g., electric stoves, air conditioners), with or without strengthened regulations and standards (e.g., residential insulation codes, tax and subsidy reforms). A deeper analysis of the measures and how they may be modelled could lead to more valuable and actionable policy insights than revenue recycling with additional co-benefits in line with other connected societal objectives such as the Sustainable development Goals (SDG 1: No poverty, SDG 7: Access to affordable and clean energy, SDG 10: Reduced inequalities, among others).

5. Conclusion

We have aimed to inform just climate policies by examining the dynamics of sub-national distributional consequences of both climate change impacts and cost-optimum mitigation policies determined by IAMs. A number of conclusions can be drawn based on the results presented in this study.

Reduced emissions in mitigation scenarios can lead to progressive distributional outcomes in the long term from avoided climate damages. The poorest income groups are most likely to suffer the most from climate damages, and thus also benefit the most from climate policy in terms of avoided damages. As climate impacts with or without mitigation increase over the century, the greatest distributional benefits of mitigation are seen only in the long term. Especially for poorer (and generally hotter) regions, the degree of regressivity prevented through avoided damages in the long term is greater than the degree of increased regressivity via higher energy expenditures in the short term. Most of these regions avoid a greater degree of increased income inequality from avoided damages in mitigation scenarios compared to the corresponding impact from unequal energy expenditures. The only exceptions are found in parts of Africa, where households are already suffering from energy poverty and low access to modern energy services.

In the absence of complementary redistributive policies, climate mitigation policies relying solely on carbon prices can lead to increased inequalities within regions through their unequal impact on residential energy expenditures. Climate policies modelled via uniform carbon prices result in an overall reduction of dependence on fossil fuels in the residential energy mix in order to meet targeted mitigation levels. At the same time, they risk exacerbating existing inequalities in energy burdens across income quintiles, with poorer quintiles being affected disproportionately higher. This is typically the case if energy expenditures represent a higher share of income. Furthermore, richer income groups can 'pay their way out of' carbon pricing by adopting cleaner and more efficient capital-intensive technologies, which poorer households often cannot afford. As a consequence,

poorer households can even descend down the energy ladder. Supporting policies which can reduce this regressivity should focus on making clean fuels affordable to poorer household (including provision of adequate infrastructure), ensuring access to basic energy services, and decarbonisation of the electricity system.

Mitigating climate change indicates eventual net-progressive outcomes, thus especially beneficial for poorer income groups, but unequal burdens and impacts need to be considered. In most regions, climate policies in the residential sector in the form of carbon pricing likely lead to net-progressive outcomes in the long term, when accounting for avoided damages, even in the absence of any modelled redistributive policy. However, in the short to mid-term, poorer income groups could likely bear the brunt of a cost-optimal carbon price without additional support to transition into a low-carbon future. Equitable, needs-based redistributive policies would allow these vulnerable populations to bear the disproportionate energy burdens, consequently avoiding regressive impact from unmitigated damages in both short and long terms. This is crucial since the potential regressivity of the distributional impacts influences the perceived fairness and thus the successful implementation of climate policies. Complementary policies incentivising the transition into clean energy use can also prevent the negative impact on health and air quality as poor income groups in many regions risk descending down the energy ladder. Addressing these equity concerns is likely to garner broad societal support for climate policy. The estimated annual global policy costs may be taken into consideration by policymakers alongside related investment needs towards equitable sustainable development (Kulkarni *et al* 2022). Considerations of fair effort sharing and just transitions of energy systems to meet global climate goals are incomplete without accounting for distributional consequences at the sub-national level.

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Data availability statement

No new data were created or analysed in this study.

Appendix

A1. IMAGE modelling framework

We apply the Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment (IMAGE) framework (Stehfest *et al* 2014) to explore the unequal impacts of a global uniform carbon price on residential energy expenditures across income groups. The IMAGE framework is an integrated assessment model (IAM) applied to study the long-term dynamics of global change in the energy and land system. The framework comprises various system dynamic sub-models, including the energy model TIMER and the climate policy cost-benefit model MIMOSA.

The energy model TIMER describes the annual demand and supply of different energy carriers for a set of 26 world regions. Changes in energy demand within the available sectors (industry, transport, residential, services, non-energy and other) are related to structural changes, autonomous and price-induced changes in energy intensity and price-based fuel substitution. Several sub-modules of TIMER simulate the various demand sectors in more detail, such as REMG for household energy use (Daioglou *et al* 2012), and NEDE for the non-energy (petrochemical) sector (Daioglou *et al* 2013). TIMER projects future energy demand for each end-use sector based on relationships between energy services and activity, the latter of which is related to economic growth (Van Vuuren *et al* 2011, Mulders *et al* 2006, Rogner 1997).

A1.1. Modelling residential energy demand

The residential energy demand sub-model in TIMER captures the different energy use characteristics of 260 represented households. Energy demand for each household is disaggregated across five end-use functions: cooking, space heating, space cooling, water heating, and appliances. Demand for each end-use is driven by household characteristics such as household size, total household expenditures (proxy for income), floor space, and ownership levels and energy efficiencies of end-use equipment or technology (e.g., appliances, stoves, heaters, insulation types).

The market share of energy carriers or technologies used is determined by a multinomial logit function, accounting for differences in relative costs and preferences per option (Van Vuuren *et al* 2011). For each end-

use function, energy carriers compete based on relative costs with each other to meet the useful energy demand. This assigns market shares to different options fulfilling a service based on their relative costs, where the cheapest option gets the largest market share, the second cheapest the second largest market share, and so on. Energy prices are based on supply curves of energy carriers (Mulders *et al* 2006, Rogner 1997). All households within a region face the same energy prices. To represent climate policy in the model, a ‘carbon price’ is introduced to induce a shift towards low-carbon technologies. In these mitigation scenarios, the household characteristics and activity levels driving total energy demand remains the same, but may be met with different choices of energy carriers through the logit function.

Additionally, households can further adopt energy-efficiency measures such as insulation to reduce demand in mitigation scenarios based on the relative costs of doing so compared to incurring additional heating costs. This dynamic is based on recent model development reported in detail in (Daioglou *et al* 2022). In short, the model accounts for regional building stocks (construction, lifetimes, decommissioning), calculation of investments in six insulation levels, inclusion of energy efficient heat pumps as a space heating technology, and possibility for households to invest in rooftop solar PV. Additionally, the model already accounts for endogenous efficiency changes in end-use energy conversion representing availability of more efficient appliances over time. Thus, although the socioeconomic household characteristics and activity level that drive the demand remain unchanged, they may be met by a slightly smaller (larger) final energy demand as households make choices towards more (less) energy efficient options available to them (see figure A11 below and figure A3 in the main article).

Correspondingly, key mitigation options in TIMER on the energy supply side include increasing the share of nuclear power and renewables in electricity generation, equipping fossil fuel technologies with Carbon Capture and Sequestration (CCS), improving energy efficiency, and reducing non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, interactions of the residential sector of the model with the energy supply system are also included through rooftop solar PV electricity generation.

Previously, these model dynamics have been used to assess the contribution of the residential sector in meeting climate mitigation targets (Daioglou *et al* 2012), the role of strategies such as behaviour change and technology adoption in this sector (Daioglou *et al* 2022, van Sluisveld *et al* 2016), and the interactions of the residential sector with the rest of the energy system (Daioglou *et al* 2013, Dagnachew *et al* 2018) in different mitigation scenarios. The model has also been used to explore pathways towards universal electricity access (Lucas *et al* 2017, Dagnachew *et al* 2017), and to universal access to clean cooking (Hof *et al* 2018) in Sub-Saharan Africa. The present work analyses the distribution of resulting energy expenditures across the modelled households, more specifically the disproportionality of additional energy expenditure burdens across increasing income levels in mitigation scenarios.

A1.2. Modelling climate damages

MIMOSA is a cost-benefit sub-model that compares marginal mitigation costs to marginal climate impacts (damages) and derives cost-optimal global emission pathways which meet cumulative end-of-century emission budget (or temperature target). The model consists of relatively simple economic and emission modules, with interactions between them occurring through damages and mitigation. It is parametrised using a set of

assumptions on damage functions, mitigation costs involving regional marginal abatement cost (MAC) curves, climate sensitivities, discount rates and socioeconomic developments (figure A2).

Apart from determining cost-optimal mitigation pathways (Van Der Wijst *et al* 2021), the model has been used to analyse the regional distribution of damages, highlighting the substantial damages in developing regions even in Paris-compliant mitigation scenarios (van der Wijst *et al* 2021). In the present work, we use the model to determine mean per capita regional damages, driven by SSP2 scenario consistent socio-economic variables (Riahi *et al* 2017) (GDP, population, emission intensity, technological growth and lifestyle etc.) and mitigation policy (cumulative emissions targets). MIMOSA uses the COACCH damage function (see further below), which translates physical impacts from emission-linked increased temperatures into economic damages using a CGE, compared to previously used damage functions in literature that relied more heavily on semi-qualitative expert assessment (Howard and Sterner 2017). The function parametrises the impact uncertainty using quantile regression to account for a broad range of sectoral impacts (van der Wijst *et al* 2023).

IMAGE models socioeconomic developments in 26 world regions as follows: Canada (CAN), USA, Mexico (MEX), Central America (RCAM), Brazil (BRA), Rest of South America (RSAM), South Africa (SAF), Rest of Southern Africa (RSAF), Northern Africa (NAF), Western Africa (WAF), Eastern Africa (EAF), Western Europe (WEU), Central Europe (CEU), Turkey (TUR), Ukraine region (UKR), Central Asia (STAN), Russia region (RUS), Middle East (ME), India, Rest of South Asia (RSAS), Indonesia region (INDO), Southeast Asia (SEAS), Japan (JAP), Korea region (KOR), China region (CHN), and Oceania (OCE). The regional groupings and the list of the countries within the regions are shown in https://models.pbl.nl/image/Region_classification_map.

A1.3. The COACCH damage function

IAMs such as MIMOSA developed to perform cost-benefit analysis (CBA) use so-called reduced-form damage functions that relate changes in global mean temperature change with aggregate economic losses. Both physical climate change impacts as well as their economic valuations are deeply uncertain and partly simply unknown. All damage functions represent the evolving “best-known” degree of climate impacts.

Earlier studies used top-down damage functions relating available empirical data on local temperatures and economic growth, calibrated using semi-quantitative expert assessments and aggregations of local impact studies related to likely climate change impacts such as flooding, sea-level rise, etc. More recently, the COACCH damage function use a cover climate impacts across a large set of sectors (agriculture, forestry, fishery, energy demand, energy supply, labour supply, riverine floods, transportation and sea-level rise). Net GDP losses in various regions and points of time are derived bottom up by including results from these individual sectoral impact models in a CGE framework. Using quantile regression, curves fitted on these points allows for inclusion of an internally explicit, consistent, and broad uncertainty ranges for use in CBA-IAMs.

A2. Modelling income distribution

A number of functional forms can be used to estimate the distribution of income, with the choice in each application based on the trade-offs between accuracy, data needs and computational requirements. Functional forms such as the Singh-Maddala distribution which involve three parameters, and the Generalised Beta II with four parameters, can offer more accuracy in fitting data (Kumar 2017), but involve computationally expensive estimation of the additional parameters for each country-year. They are better suited to applications with limited geographic and temporal scope. Among two-parameter functional forms, the log-normal function offers the best fit to many survey data sets compared to others such as Weibull or Pareto distributions (Lubrano 2012), and uses available scenario-consistent values for the two parameters to perform scenario analyses (Boccanfuso et al 2008, Soergel et al 2021).

The distribution of incomes within countries is modelled following the log-normal probability density function given by:

$$pdf(Y) = \frac{1}{Y\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{(\ln Y - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \tag{A1}$$

where Y is the total income, and the two parameters describing the scale (μ) and shape (σ) of the distribution are defined with the mean per capita income (Y_{mean}), the Gini coefficient (G), and the normal cumulative distribution ϕ as follows:

$$\mu = e^{(Y_{mean} + \frac{\sigma^2}{2})} \text{ and } \sigma = \sqrt{2\pi} \phi^{-1}\left(\frac{G+1}{2}\right) \tag{A2}$$

Total income (Y) as a share of the national GDP is represented by total household expenditures from the World Bank's World Development Indicators database as a proxy (World Bank 2015).

$$E_{country} = GDP_{country} \text{ Total_household_expenditure_share_of_}GDP_{country} \tag{A3}$$

For each country-year, total household expenditures ($E_{country}$) are first determined as shares of total GDP, and then allocated to urban and rural areas

$$E_{urban} = a \eta_{urban} E_{country} \text{ and } E_{rural} = a \eta_{rural} E_{country} \tag{A4}$$

where the parameters η_{urban} and η_{rural} are derived through a linear regression driven by urbanisation rates and survey data on mean per capita urban and rural expenditure levels used in (Steckel et al 2023) and kindly shared with us by the authors. The scaling factor a is chosen such that the total household expenditures in urban and rural areas add up to match the national total.

For each country-year, a Monte Carlo simulation of the lognormal probability density function is performed ($n = 10000$). The results are ordered and mean per capita expenditures for each population quintile are

calculated, analogous to income quintiles. The simulation is repeated for urban and rural areas to correspondingly determine mean per capita household expenditures for five urban and rural quintiles respectively.

Income quintiles are first calculated at the country-level because a) Gini coefficient data is most frequently available at country-level and, b) aggregating Gini coefficients of regions significantly underestimates the true Gini coefficients of the constituent sub-regions (Darvas 2016). The quintiles are then aggregated to 26 world regions to allow coupling with the TIMER model for mitigation impacts, and the MIMOSA model for damages. To do this, total quintile expenditures and corresponding populations at each time-step are summed into IMAGE regions from constituent countries. Per capita values are then recalculated.

Table A1. Data sources for modelled country level income distribution

Variable	Historical data	Scenario projections
GDP	World Bank data ^a	IIASA SSP database ^b
Population	World Bank data ^c	IIASA SSP database ^b
Urbanisation rate (% population)	World Bank data ^d	IIASA SSP database ^b
Total household expenditure per capita	World Bank data ^e	Derived by applying SSP GDP per capita growth rates to total household expenditure per capita
Gini	Based on (Narayan <i>et al</i> 2022)	IIASA SSP database ^b , based on (Rao <i>et al</i> 2018)

^a GDP per capita (constant 2015 US\$) | Data (worldbank.org)

^b This data is based on the SSP database hosted by the IIASA Energy Program at <https://tntcat.iiasa.ac.at/SspDb>.

^c Population, total | Data (worldbank.org)

^d Urban population (% of total population) | Data (worldbank.org)

^e Households and NPISHs final consumption expenditure (% of GDP) | Data (worldbank.org)

Data

Historical data for GDP, population, and urbanisation rate (i.e., percentage of population living in urban areas) are based on World Bank datasets, while baseline projections are based on the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). Historical data on household expenditure per capita from the World Bank is projected along the 21st century along SSP GDP per capita growth rates. For each country, these are allocated to urban and rural areas based on urbanisation rates and national survey data on mean per-capita urban and rural expenditure levels (see section A2). We overcome the well-known gaps in coverage of historical Gini data from global datasets such as World Bank data by using a recently published dataset (Narayan *et al* 2022) which imputes missing World Bank Gini data using principal component analysis. This historical data is combined with Gini projections from the IIASA SSP database based on (Rao *et al* 2018). All monetary data is converted into constant 2005 USD prices in IMAGE model. Unless otherwise specified, all further monetary values presented in this article are expressed in 2005 USD terms.

A3. Calculating the suits index

We calculate the additional energy burdens across income quintiles as a result of introducing carbon pricing in the residential energy sector. To ascertain the overall distributional effect on households, we now assess how the additional budget shares spent on energy expenditures differ across income groups. If the additional budget shares are proportionally to increasing income the policy is distributionally neutral, and progressive (regressive) if they decrease (increase) with income.

The Suits index provides a useful way of capturing this using the concept of relative concentration curves, similar to the Lorenz curves used to calculate the better-known Gini index (Suits 1977). The index has been used as a measure of tax progressivity for example of wage taxes, but also in previous assessments of carbon tax progressivity in non-IAM studies, mostly focusing on case studies involving the transport sector in different countries and years (Burtraw *et al* 2009, Sterner 2012). The index measures the deviation of a tax from income proportionality (Andersson and Atkinson 2020, Arcarons and Calonge 2015) with values bound by the interval $(-1, 1)$ or equivalently $(-100, 100)$. Positive values indicate progressivity, or that higher income groups are impacted progressively higher and vice versa. A Suit index of zero indicates neutral incidence, i.e., impacts are exactly proportional by increasing incomes.

Strictly speaking, the IMAGE model does not apply a tax. However, the additional energy burdens represent a greater share of the same total household expenditures in the scenario with carbon pricing compared to the baseline scenario. Since the total household expenditures (a proxy for incomes) in each of the modelled 260 quintiles are unchanged between the two scenarios, the additional energy burdens are analogous to a tax for the purpose of this calculation.

It is important to note that the index only pertains to the differences of relative impacts across incomes, irrespective of the scale. For example, if the richest income groups spend an additional 0.1% of total household expenditures on energy compared to an additional 0.2% spent by the poorest, this could lead to very high Suits index values indicating very progressive outcomes. Care must be taken in interpreting these results by looking at the scale of underlying respective impacts.

Figure A4 shows the relative concentration curve (line *e*) representing the cumulative shares of incident tax, C_t , over cumulative shares of income, C_y . The line *e* represents a distributionally neutral tax incidence, perfectly proportional to incomes. Geometrically, the Suits index is calculated using K , the area bounded by OAB , and L , the area bounded by $OABC$ so that

$$\begin{aligned}
 S &= \left(\frac{K - L}{K} \right) = 1 - \left(\frac{L}{K} \right) = 1 - (1/K) \int_0^1 C_t(p) dC_y(p) \\
 &= 1 - (1/0.5) \int_0^1 C_t(p) dC_y(p) = 1 - 2 \int_0^1 C_t(p) dC_y(p)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{A5}$$

where $C_t(p)$ is cumulative proportion of tax paid by the p^{th} share of the population and $C_y(p)$ is its cumulative income, defined as

$$C_t(p) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^p T_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n T_i} \text{ and } C_y(p) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^p Y_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i}
 \tag{A6}$$

where T_i is the tax paid by the i^{th} income group, Y_i is its income, and n is the number of income groups. In our application, the changes in energy burdens are found to be negative for some richer quintiles in the long term, the cumulative tax term $C_t(p)$ is adapted to accommodate negative values as

$$C_t(p) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^p T_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n T_i^+ - \sum_{i=1}^n T_i^-}
 \tag{A7}$$

where T_i^+ and T_i^- are the positive and negative tax values summed separately to avoid potential division by zero.

A4. Extra Figures

A4.1. Energy expenditures impacts

Scenario time-trends—Mean per capita energy expenditure for selected regions

Figure A5. Mean per capita energy expenditure for selected regions in (a) baseline SSP2, (b) 1.5 °C mitigation and (c) 2 °C mitigation scenarios.

Additional energy burden for all quintiles in 1.5 °C mitigation scenario

Figure A6. Additional energy burdens (energy expenditure as fraction of income) for all quintiles in 1.5 °C scenario relative to Baseline in (a) Short term, (b) Mid term, (c) Long term.

Additional energy burden for urban and rural quintiles in mitigation scenarios

Figure A8. Additional energy burdens (energy expenditure as fraction of income) for bottom and top rural quintiles in 1.5 °C scenario relative to Baseline in (a) Short term, (b) Mid term, (c) Long term.

Figure A10. Additional energy burdens (energy expenditure as fraction of income) for bottom and top rural quintiles in 2 °C scenario relative to Baseline in (a) Short term, (b) Mid term, (c) Long term.

Changes in residential energy mix corresponding to unequal additional energy burdens

Figure A11. Residential energy mix in 2050 for in the Baseline and 1.5 °C scenarios for the poorest urban quintiles (top panels), and the richest (bottom panels).

Direct residential sector emissions for richest and poorest quintiles

Figure A13. Direct emissions from residential sector energy use for bottom and top urban quintiles in 1.5 °C scenario relative to Baseline in (a) Short term, (b) Mid term, (c) Long term.

Figure A14. Direct emissions from residential sector energy use for bottom and top rural quintiles in the Baseline (SSP2) scenario relative to Baseline in (a) Short term, (b) Mid term, (c) Long term.

Suits indices for unequal energy expenditure impacts

Gini change due to unequal energy expenditure impacts

A4.2. Climate change impacts (damages)

Scenario time-trends—Mean per capita damages for selected regions

Avoided per capita climate damages (as fraction of income) for top and bottom quintiles in 2 °C scenario relative to Baseline

Suits indices for unequal distribution of avoided damages

Figure A23. Suits indices for unequal distribution of avoided damages in the 1.5 °C scenario.

Gini change due to unequal distribution of avoided damages

A4.3. Combined distributional impacts from energy expenditures and damages

Suits indices

Figure A25. Suits indices for combined unequal impacts from energy expenditures and avoided damages in 1.5 °C scenario.

Gini change

Figure A26. Gini change due to combined unequal impacts from energy expenditures and avoided damages in the 1.5 °C scenario.

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